

PLUCKING BUTTONS: AN ALTERNATE SOFT BUTTON INPUT METHOD ON TOUCH SCREENS FOR MUSICAL INTERACTION

Edward Jangwon Lee

Audio & Interactive Media Lab
Graduate School of Culture Technology, KAIST
291 Daehak-ro, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon, Korea
noshel@kaist.ac.kr

Woon Seung Yeo

Audio & Interactive Media Lab
Graduate School of Culture Technology, KAIST
291 Daehak-ro, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon, Korea
woony@kaist.edu

ABSTRACT

This article introduces *plucking buttons*, an alternate method of interacting with soft buttons on touch screens that can provide more sound parameters that are expected to enhance expressiveness in digital music. Rather than pushing buttons, users are required to start and end touches inside and outside of the button, respectively, in order to activate the button. This gesture is similar to flicking (swiping) gestures on touch screens and plucking strings on musical instruments. Advantages of this button and gesture include providing extra sound parameters, preventing accidental input, and not requiring additional screen space. The largest challenge of this gesture to be used in music is the possible delay and inaccuracy of input due to relatively complex interaction, and this is tested by comparing two input types: plucking vs. pushing buttons. Test results suggest that plucking can be used, but can be efficiently used after training. Melodic musical tasks are also executed, and users were able to successfully play a simple song.

1. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of programmable touch screen interfaces has provided a versatile platform to build various types of digital musical interfaces with a very low production cost. Moreover, nowadays touch interfaces are widely adopted on mobile devices, such as smartphones and tablet PCs, and offers high computation power – powerful enough to synthesize and play real-time audio [1], and this has enabled digital musicians to have a powerful, programmable, and yet affordable digital musical interface with extreme mobility.

The versatility of touch screen programming and continuous multitouch features of these devices enabled the development of various types of user interface control components and input gestures. Nevertheless, buttons, that require tapping interaction in a predefined and restricted space on screen, seem to be the most popular control in touch screens. However, buttons on touch screens (soft

buttons) differ from their real-life counterparts (hard buttons), as most devices do not provide haptic feedback and are not pressure-sensitive. The absence of pressure sensing leaves buttons prone to accidental input and also exhibits a loss of touch information. In a musical context, touch screen buttons have a risk of playing unintended notes, and the loss of information results in less sound parameters, which in turn can imply reduced expressiveness.

As a remedy for these weaknesses, this research proposes an alternate method of interacting with soft buttons on touch screens: *plucking*, which involves swiping gestures from inside to outside of the button. Requiring the touch to start inside a button and to end outside is expected to prevent accidental touches, while providing extra touch information that will grant additional expressiveness. However, as the proposed gesture is more complex than tapping, user tests are required to determine whether this gesture is usable for musical needs.

2. PLUCKING GESTURES

Unlike traditional musical instruments with strings, touch screens do not have strings that can be plucked. This section describes the plucking gesture in traditional music, and sets an alternate definition of plucking that can be applied on touch screens.

2.1 Plucking Gestures in Musical Instruments

In music, plucking is done to generate sound by applying force on a string of instruments, such as the guitar. This force can be applied either by using fingers or plectrums (picks). In detail, the plucking gesture can be divided as a threefold process: (a) holding, (b) pulling, and (c) releasing. *Holding* initiates a pluck by selecting and holding a string that is to be excited, and *pulling* repositions the string to a different location, thereby accumulating force. Finally, *releasing* the string finalizes the gesture and sets the string into vibration, which is transferred throughout the instrument to emit sound. Figure 1 illustrates the plucking process.

Normally, musical instruments in the chordophone family maintain a high tension their stretched strings. Therefore, a minimum amount of force is required to accumulate enough force to generate sound. This enables the second step of plucking – pulling – to be a very short distance, and this causes the plucking process to go through the three

Figure 1. Holding, pulling and releasing.

steps almost instantly. However, varying the technique of any step results in tonal variety, which grants expressiveness and nuance to the player.

In terms of interaction, each step of plucking has its own role. *Holding* selects the target of interaction (string to be plucked), *pulling* determines the result variation (loudness and other tonal attributes), and *releasing* indicates that the user is ready to output a result, based on the two previous steps (set strings into vibration and generate sound).

2.2 Plucking Gestures in Touch Screens

In the context of touch screen environments, the threefold definition of plucking gestures – *holding*, *pulling*, and *releasing* – can be interpreted in terms of touch events: touch down (or touch start), touch move, and touch up (or touch end). Although this is a general lifespan of touchscreen interactions, the implications of each phase follow the three plucking stages. Starting a touch selects the control to be activated, moving the touch determines additional attributes, and finally, releasing the touch outputs a result calculated from the two previous steps.

The main difference between real string instruments and touch screens is that there is no real string to be plucked. Therefore, the user cannot feel any force being accumulated during the pull, nor the strings themselves. This characteristic can be used as an advantage to plucking gestures. While real strings normally are not to be pulled over adjacent strings, in touch interfaces, after a touch start point is decided, the touch can be pulled over other controls without activating them (Figure 2). This implies that no additional screen space is required to implement plucking gestures in touch screens – buttons, which serve as touch start (holding) points, can be placed nearly as that of ordinary types.

Figure 2. Plucking on touch screens. (a) Button 1 is pressed (touch down or *held*), (b) additional information is gathered while touch moves (touch move or *pull*), and (c) releasing triggers output combining Button 1 and the touch move data (touch end or *release*). Button 2 does not interact during the touch.

3. POSSIBILITIES OF PLUCKING GESTURES AS A MUSICAL GESTURE ON TOUCH SCREENS

In this section, we further discuss the qualifications of plucking gestures on touch screens, which is defined in the previous section. We believe that plucking grants additional musical expressiveness while not requiring extra screen space, and that users can easily execute plucking gestures, due to the similarity of plucking gestures to swiping.

3.1 Additional Sound Parameters

Nowadays, in the professional music industry, there is a trend of releasing touch interface versions of their previously released musical instruments. While this movement allowed users to purchase instruments at a more affordable price, the limitations of touch interfaces prevented those from the successful translation of certain aspects of the original hardware. For example, the well-known sampler AKAI MPC has its Apple iPad version, named iMPC. Although it is offered at a very low price, several features of the original MPC had to be omitted: velocity (pressure on pad when first pressed) and aftertouch (changing pressure during press). These two features use pressure information and enable users to input additional sound parameters when and while pressing a pad. However, the iPad version does not support this, as the device does not have sensors to dynamically measure pressure applied by users. As a remedy, AKAI sells an optional hardware named MPC FLY, which has external trigger pads with pressure sensors and an interface to the iPad and iMPC software (Figure 3).¹

Figure 3. (left to right) AKAI MPC, iMPC and MPC Fly. Limitations of touch interfaces cause loss of gestural information, and external devices are in the market to mitigate such losses.

The example of iMPC – the AKAI MPC on iPad – illustrates the loss of gestural information during the translation from dedicated musical hardware to touch interface tablet PC software. Rather than fully using the pressure changes during pressing trigger pads, the tablet version generates sound upon touch events and prolonged touches can only control the length of sound – that is, on and off.

However, actual touch events convey more information than touch start and end. Between the beginning and ending of a touch, the touching finger is able to move to another location, and this movement contains a vast amount of information that can be used in designing a more complex interaction.

Dobrian (2006) argues that “expressive control relies on more sophisticated use of the control input information”

¹ Photographs of the MPC products are retrieved from AKAI Professional website, <http://akaipro.com>.

[2]. Pushing buttons and generating sound upon touch start on touch interfaces clearly discards gestural information that is generated after the touch starts. The most attractive aspect of plucking gestures on touch interfaces is that the three phases of touch events (touch down, touch move and touch up) are fully usable. Plucking gestures can incorporate touch movements and touch ending events as additional sound parameters, and thereby offer more expressiveness.

Compared to preexisting velocity simulation techniques such as touch size detection (harder touches activates a larger area on the screen) or accelerometer value changes (harder touches cause more movement of the device), plucking is a different approach. That is, rather than capturing the touch force itself, plucking requires additional interaction (pulling and releasing) in order to collect more data from one gesture.

3.2 Widely Used Gesture on Touch Interfaces

Although the proposed plucking gesture seems to be more complex than pressing buttons, the gesture itself is only a marginal cost added to *flicking*. Flicking gestures, which are mostly used in turning pages, takes all touch data (start, move and end) into account and accordingly scrolls the screen. Usually, flicking requires the user to move the touch quickly, and the velocity of movement should not decrease near touch end. The user executes flicking by touching an arbitrary point within the content, move to touch quickly towards a desired direction, and ends the touch without slowing down. Plucking gestures in this research slightly adds cost to flicking: (a) plucking requires the user to pinpoint the starting point of touch, so that the desired control to activate can be determined before the touch moves, and (b) the distance of pulling should be taken into account.

3.3 Avoids Accidental Input

One of the largest problems of touch interfaces is accidental input problems. In most real-life hard buttons, such as computer keyboards, users can place their fingers or hands on the button without activating it. However, on touch screens, buttons can be activated by the slightest touch, and this aspect is a risk to take in music, as well as other fields of applications.

Although the proposed gesture, *plucking buttons*, heighten the complexity of activating buttons, this complexity can serve as a mitigation to such accidental inputs. In order to activate a button with plucking, the user must start and end the touch inside and outside the button, respectively. Therefore, as real-life keyboards, users are able to place their hands on the buttons while they are unused, and no output is produced. Even after a button has been pressed (*holding*) and the finger has moved out of the button (*pulling*), simply returning inside the button cancels the activation.

4. TEST DESIGN AND DATA COLLECTION

In this section, a test design that can determine whether plucking gestures can be used as a musical gesture on touch

screen environments is described. After highlighting the anticipated difficulties of plucking, musical tasks [3] are devised to test each issue. Quantitative and qualitative methods are employed, in rhythmic and melodic musical tasks, respectively.

4.1 Challenges of Pulling Gestures in Music

Cost of Interaction. The highest obstacle of employing plucking gestures in music is the cost of interaction. In order to fully utilize touch data generated throughout the touch lifespan, the final sound output should be delayed until the touch event completes. Therefore, the total time required from player intention to sound output increases, and only a marginal amount of such time increase can be critical in real-time situations such as live performances. This test focuses on the human ability to rapidly execute plucking gestures enough to match their intentions and keep up to tempo.

Location of touch release. Among the three steps of plucking, *pulling* surely is the most time-consuming step. In order to minimize the cost of interaction described above, the time used in pulling should be as short as possible. Another challenging point stems from here: whether players can freely control the location of releasing. Choosing a point to touch on the screen is relatively easy, compared to pinpointing the location of releasing touch after rapid movement.

4.2 Rhythmic Musical Task

Staying "*in the pocket*", that is, being able to keep up tempo, is one of the most important virtues of playing an instrument. Therefore, requiring additional time in musical interaction can be intolerable. As plucking gestures on touch interfaces clearly require more time compared to pushing buttons, proper user testing is crucial to approve the usability of plucking in music. To test the possibilities of keeping musical tempo while plucking, a quantitative test method is devised that records the time deviation between played notes (onsets) and prerecorded metronome pulses (click onsets). Many examples of this type of experiment, which require users to interact referring to auditory cues, can be found in the sensorimotor synchronization (SMS) literature [4] [5].

4.2.1 Task Description

The objective of this task is to execute a simple test employing descriptive statistics to evaluate the rhythmic difference between pushing and plucking gestures.

A rhythmic musical task is prepared, requiring users to play notes at every one beat. A prerecorded common timed metronome track is played for a total of eight bars. The first four bars are pre-rolls, enabling users to become accustomed to the tempo. Although interaction details are recorded throughout the eight bars (32 beats), only the latter two (8 beats) are to be used in analysis. User tests are to be executed in three different tempi: 60, 120 and 180 beats per minute (bpm). Two versions of touch interface applications are prepared with one large button each, differing in interaction style: (a) sound generation upon pushing (touch

down event) and (b) sound generation upon plucking gesture.

4.2.2 Measurement and Hypothesis

While the prerecorded metronome track is playing, every touch interaction is recorded. Afterwards, the recorded information is processed by hand in order to extract the final eight touches (onsets). Each touch time is measured as a millisecond representation of the current sample number of the metronome track (16bit, 44,100Hz sample rate) being played at the time of touch: that is, touch down time for pushing and touch up time for plucking. As the metronome onset time can be easily calculated, onset asynchronies can be calculated as the difference between metronome onset times and time of touches.

For each participant, mean onset asynchronies and standard deviations are calculated. As there are two different input methods (pushing and plucking) and three different tempi (60, 120, and 180bpm), each participant generates six sets of data.

We expect that the increased cost will increase a participant's mean asynchrony, as plucking is clearly a costlier interaction than pushing. However, as ending touches (lifting finger off screen) requires less physical movement than starting touches (placing finger on screen), in low tempi the standard deviation of plucking might be lower than pushing.

4.3 Melodic Musical Task

In addition to the quantitative rhythmic musical task, a melodic task to assess the playability is devised. This test is designed as a qualitative test, and feedbacks from users are collected during and after a time of exploring, free-playing, and being asked to play a simple song. Playing a simple song intends to determine whether users are able to play desired notes at a desired timing, without accidental input or misplayed notes.

4.4 Sample Demography and size

The test sample includes ten participants, including three professional musicians. Each participant was given three to five minutes of guided exploration of the interface, and the rhythmic test was executed afterwards. After the rhythmic musical task, users were asked to execute the melodic musical task.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

A simple touch application is implemented to meet our testing needs. The application, named *Pull*, is developed on Apple's New iPad with iOS 6.1 using Cocos2D/Box2D game development framework.² Multitouch feature is also included, to enable multi-note chords and drum patterns.

Timing. For precise interaction time recording relative to the metronome in rhythmic musical tasks, the MoMu toolkit [6] is used as the audio engine, running at 44,100Hz sample rate. Metronomes in each test tempo are pre-recorded

and stored in .wav format (16bit, 44,100Hz sample rate), and user interaction timings are stored as the time elapsed since metronome start (calculated from the current sample number played). This method is similar to the method used in Kim et al. (2012) [7].

Sound generation. Instruments samples from Apple Logic Pro 9 were recorded as .wav files and preloaded. The samples include one octave of a marimba in C major scale (eight notes; C4 to C5), and a four-note TR808 drum kit (open and closed hi-hats, kick and snare drums).

Figure 4. (upper) Prototype user interface. The grey circle in the center is the main button. After touching the innermost circle, the touch is moved to a desired arc, which each represents a different note, and releases the touch to generate sound with the corresponding pitch. Multi-touches are available. (lower) Pitch versus distance and angle mapping used in the initial melodic musical task.

5.1 User Interface

Figure 4 shows the prototype user interface. The grey innermost circle is the main button which users start the pulling gesture. The colored outer circles serve as a guideline for users to pinpoint their touch release location. After a *touch down*, *touch move*, and *touch up* event cycle is ended, the application calculates the move distance between the touch start and end points as well as the angle of movement in ra-

² <http://www.cocos2d-iphone.org>

dians, ranging between 0 and 2π . For each touch, a small ball is generated and follows the finger, to indicate the current touch position. On touch release, the ball rapidly returns to the original location.

5.2 Musical Mappings

The interface in upper portion of Figure 4 has only one button in the center of screen, with colored circle guidelines for plucking. Plucking gestures on this interface is implemented as follows. After starting the touch in the center, the touch is moved to a desired location in the outer circles, where each arc represents a different note. Arcs with the same color represent identical pitch. Releasing the touch inside the center circle does not produce sound; the touch *must* be moved outside the center circle and be released in order to play a note. Further details on the mappings can be found in the lower portion of Figure 4.

For the rhythmic musical task, an alternate one-button interface that generates sound upon touch down events is also implemented.

As this research focuses on the possibility of using plucking gestures on touch screens, only one button has been implemented. However, after user tests, another user interface employing several buttons has been developed, and will be introduced in section 6.

6. DATA ANALYSIS

6.1 Rhythmic Musical Task

The mean asynchronies and standard deviations of each participant are described in Table 1. Most of the participants showed a positive shift in mean asynchronies when plucking, suggesting that the increased cost of plucking gestures generates a systematic difference between the mean asynchronies of the two input methods. While most sensorimotor synchronization experiments exhibit negative asynchronies [5], frequent occurrence of positive means might imply that the increased interaction cost of plucking is larger than expected.

Standard deviations show less differences between the two input methods, which range between less than 1ms to 26ms. In 60bpm, most participants show an increase in variability while plucking. However, as the tempo increases, plucking begins to exhibit more stable results compared to pushing: six out of ten participants showed decreased standard deviation compared to pushing.

Data of full-time professional musicians can be found in participants 4, 6, and 7: a guitarist, drummer, and pianist, respectively. The guitarist (participant 4) was not able to pluck stably ($SD = 56ms$) in 60bpm, but in 120 and 180bpm plucking showed less standard deviation than pushing. The drummer (participant 6) showed superior performance in pushing, but relatively poor in plucking. Regarding the fact that the test began with 60bpm and towards higher tempi and that plucking is a newly introduced musical gesture, the test results might be handicapped with lack of training, as the drummer's standard deviation in 120bpm drastically rises (1ms to 25ms).

To further analyze the effects of training, participant 10 (non-musician) was offered several iterations of the experiment for fifteen minutes. After mentioning that he realized how it should be done, participant 10 was able to achieve stable results in both mean and variability. This suggests that the increased cost of interaction might be overcome through training.

6.2 Melodic Musical Task

Users were asked to freely explore the interface described in Figure 4 under our supervision and guidance for approximately five minutes, and play a popular song, "Twinkle, Twinkle, Little Star". Most of the users claimed that although playing the song was not impossible, they could not play the song fast enough due to the difficulties of pinpointing the touch end location. As the initial musical mapping mapped pitch to pull distance, users had to concentrate on precisely ending touch moves at the next note to be played. This caused users to execute the plucking gesture extremely slowly.

Based on the feedbacks above, we concluded that the one-button plucking interface with pitch mapped to pulling distance (Figure 4) is inappropriate in a sense that pulling distance cannot be easily controlled, and another user interface with multiple buttons and different musical mapping has been implemented.

Figure 5. An alternate user interface with different musical mapping. Each circular button is mapped to a different pitch in the C major scale, and the pulling distance determines the amplitude gain.

The alternate interface, depicted in Figure 5, has seven colored buttons on the upper two lines, and four grey buttons on the lower line. Each of the colored button has been assigned a different pitch: C4 to C5, in C major scale. For the lower buttons, closed hi-hat, opened hi-hat, kick drum, and snare drum has been assigned. The pulling distance of pluck determines the gain of generated sound, ranging from 0 to 3. Further pulling results in louder sound.

An identical melodic musical task was executed with the new interface, and users commented that they were much

part.	Mean Asynchrony (ms)						Standard Deviation (ms)					
	60bpm		120bpm		180bpm		60bpm		120bpm		180bpm	
	push	pluck	push	pluck	push	pluck	push	pluck	push	pluck	push	pluck
1	16	-10	-17	4	-9	28	25	35	17	22	11	17
2	-54	-75	-24	-34	-24	56	31	24	30	39	12	20
3	-9	-18	-24	27	-2	-6	40	25	21	39	20	8
4*	-5	26	3	19	-3	17	19	56	14	12	15	14
5	-56	23	56	1	-10	-3	17	30	18	17	28	25
6*	-8	26	-14	50	-20	52	20	22	1	25	12	14
7*	-30	-42	19	25	9	8	22	45	15	16	13	9
8	-33	-97	-15	-12	-30	28	27	35	33	34	42	16
9	-55	-38	-28	-13	9	12	36	24	14	9	9	6
10**	-74	43	-87	-73	-61	-31	30	19	27	25	17	20

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the collected data from ten participants. Higher mean asynchronies and lower standard deviations among the two input types, pushing and plucking, are highlighted in boldface. Most of the participants show a considerable amount of positive shift in their mean asynchronies while plucking, which suggest the increased cost of interaction. As the tempo increases, plucking gradually begins to exhibit lower standard deviations compared to pushing. Participants 4, 6, and 7 are professional musicians. Participant 10 has been trained through several iterations of the experiment.

more comfortable, as the interface had similarities with piano keys (left to right layout with higher pitches on the right) and trigger pads (grid layout of identically shaped buttons). Playability was also enhanced, and almost every test subject was able to play a simple song without difficulties.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

Plucking gestures on plucking buttons, which require the user to hold and pull a touch outside the button in order to generate output upon releasing, is a new type of musical interaction on touch screens. We believe that plucking buttons can contribute in the field of digital music by allowing more sound parameters to be mapped on a single button and providing a means of preventing accidental input – with an everyday gesture that is similar to flicking or swiping. Although the proposed gesture adds interaction cost, the costs are shown to be affordable through training, and the benefits cannot be neglected.

We are actively seeking for more possibilities of plucking. The plucking gesture implemented in this research only considers touch start and end points – the touch move path is not considered in the musical mapping. Adding parameters related to touch movement, such as acceleration, will surely produce interesting results. However, as plucking is a relatively small gesture, excessive sound parameters mapped to the gesture might cause confusion and difficulties to properly play, therefore caution is required.

8. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS AND ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

This research has been graciously supported by the funding of Korea Creative Contents Agency (KOCCA). Additional information on this research and video clips of plucking

buttons and gestures can be found in the author’s website: <http://aimlab.kaist.ac.kr/~noshel/plucking>.

9. REFERENCES

- [1] G. Wang, G. Essl, and H. Penttinen, “Do mobile phones dream of electric orchestras?” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Sound and Music Computing (ICMC)*, Belfast, 2013.
- [2] C. Dobrian and D. Koppelman, “The ‘E’ in NIME: Musical expression with new computer interfaces,” in *Proc. Conf. New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME)*, Paris, 2006, pp. 277–282.
- [3] M. M. Wanderley, “Evaluation of input devices for musical expression: Borrowing tools from hci,” *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 62–76, 2002.
- [4] B. H. Repp and A. Penel, “Auditory dominance in temporal processing: New evidence from synchronization with simultaneous visual and auditory sequences,” *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 1085–1099, 2002.
- [5] B. H. Repp, “Sensorimotor synchronization: A review of the tapping literature,” *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 969–992, 2005.
- [6] N. J. Bryan, J. Herrera, J. Oh, and G. Wang, “Momu: A mobile music toolkit,” in *Proc. Conf. New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME)*, Sydney, 2010, pp. 174–177.
- [7] H. S. Kim, B. Kaneshiro, and J. Berger, “Tap-it: An ios app for sensori-motor synchronization experiments,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Music Perception and Cognition*, Thessaloniki, 2012, pp. 528–531.